

DIAMAS launches an open call to identify reference materials

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

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As part of its scope to support Open Access Diamond and institutional publishing, DIAMAS is launching a community call!

We are looking for resources such as **guidelines, best practices, training materials, toolkits**, and **documentation** which address Journal funding; Ownership and governance; Open Science practices; Editorial quality, management and research integrity; Technical service efficiency; Visibility; and Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI).

This information will be used to create a registry of reference materials that will be made freely available for further use. By identifying resources for the DIAMAS registry you will become part of a community that helps to improve the efficiency and quality of institutional publishing.

Please use the [online documentation form](#) to identify resources – this should only take 10 minutes. More details can be found below:

How?

Please help us identify resources such as

- guidelines,
- best practices,
- training materials,
- toolkits,
- documentation
- Non-textual resources and material types (e.g., presentations, recordings, tools)

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addressing aspects of journal funding; Ownership and governance; Open Science practices; Editorial quality, management and research integrity; Technical service efficiency; Visibility; and Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI).

DIAMAS supports multilingualism and aims to **gather resources in various languages** to compile a registry with global relevance. If the resource is available in a language other than English, a translation of the title and a short account of its content may be provided in English.

Who can answer the call?

- Librarians,
- Editors,
- Publishers,
- RPOs (unis, scholarly societies, research centres) engaged in publishing activities, service providers,
- institutions designing policies (national/international level),
- coalitions/institutions developing standards or supporting publishers in adopting standards.

Deadline: Please answer our call by the 7th of July.

Contact: If you have any more questions do not hesitate to get in touch with DIAMAS Open Science Project officer Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou (irakleitos.souyioultzoglou@operas-eu.org).

We encourage you to join us in identifying resources for the DIAMAS registry of reference materials and become part of a community that actively participates in the development of a portal and knowledge-exchange hub to improve the efficiency and quality of institutional publishing.

Please use the online documentation form to identify resources in all languages and formats.

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